

THE COUNCIL OF NICAEA & THE INDIAN CRITIQUE OF CHRISTIAN DOGMAS

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Abstract: Within Indian Catholic theology, there exists an ancient and distinguished tradition of critique directed at dogma. This critique appears in two forms. The “soft” version accepts the truth of dogma but calls for reformulation in Indian categories, citing its Hellenization. The “hard” version sees dogma as both constrained and dispensable. While this critique has often focused on Chalcedon, it applies equally to the Nicene dogma of the Son’s consubstantiality with the Father. This article does not reconstruct the theological debate at the Council of Nicaea *per se*, but uses it as a case study to test the critique. The paper argues that while cultural translation – the soft form – has merit, the hard form fails. The Nicene dogma is indispensable, since without a consubstantial Son there is no salvation. The real task is inculturation: expressing this doctrinal cornerstone faithfully within Indian conceptual and linguistic frameworks.

Keywords: Indian theology, Nicaea, Christian Dogmas, Two Powers in Heaven.

INTRODUCTION

Within the broader landscape of Indian theology, one finds an established and venerable line of thought that critically engages with the claims of dogmatic theology. This critique

appears in two main forms. In its “soft” form, it accepts the validity and relevance of the dogma but argues that it should be reformulated using Indian conceptual and linguistic categories. The underlying concern here is its Hellenization—the view that the dogma’s current formulation is a historically conditioned product of the Greek intellectual tradition, and therefore not culturally neutral. In its “hard” form, the critique regards the dogma not only as the product of Hellenization, but also as a constraining formulation that limits the mystery of faith and narrows the experience of God to the boundaries of a particular conceptual system. Its relevance is challenged, too: The path of dogma, so to speak, is challenged by the mystical path: in other words, *doxa* – knowledge articulated in doctrinal form – is placed in tension with *praxis*, the lived experience of the divine. In this perspective, it is not theological formulations but direct experience that constitutes the privileged way of encountering God. This critique has most often been directed against the Chalcedonian definition of Christ’s dual nature, which is seen as deeply embedded in a Hellenistic conceptual framework.¹ Far less attention, however, has been given to another central dogma: the Nicene affirmation of the consubstantiality of the Father and the Son. The critique of the Chalcedonian dogma – whether in its “soft” form of Hellenization or in its “hard” form of constraint – can, in fact, be equally applied to the Nicene dogma.

This article does not attempt a historical reconstruction of the Council of Nicaea but uses it as a case study to evaluate the critique of Christian dogma in Indian theology. The central claim is that while the “soft” critique – which calls for cultural translation – has some merit, the “hard” critique – which dismisses dogmas as dispensable – fails in the case of Nicaea. The Nicene affirmation that the Son is consubstantial with the Father did not arise from speculative

¹ See for example V.C. Samuel, *The Council of Chalcedon Re-examined* (Delhi: ISPCK, 2001), which is a Syrian interpretation of Chalcedon.

fusion with Greek philosophy, but from the urgent need to acknowledge the salvific mediation of Christ. By doing so, the Council Fathers safeguarded the essential core of the Christian faith. If Christ were not fully God, His salvific work would be incomplete, and the theological, liturgical, and doctrinal fabric of Christianity would collapse. Greek philosophical terms were employed, but the Fathers used them deliberately, aware of their limits, to articulate the indispensable truth of Christ’s divinity. Thus, Hellenization shaped expression but not substance. The “soft” critique rightly highlights the need for inculturation into Indian categories, but what is to be translated is not a culturally bound opinion but a universal doctrinal cornerstone. The “hard” critique, by contrast, misjudges the non-negotiable role of the Nicene dogma. The task is not to discard but to faithfully communicate its salvific truth in Indian contexts.

This paper is organized into three sections. The first provides a concise account of the Indian theological unease regarding dogmas. The second outlines the central question confronted at the Council of Nicaea and the solution adopted by the Council. The third explores the implications of this solution for addressing the Indian theological unease.

1. INDIAN THEOLOGY AND DOGMA

In this section, we will trace a schematic and selective account of the uneasiness expressed by some Indian theologians toward Christian dogmas, without attempting a systematic treatment of the subject. The first case we will examine is that of Aiyadurai Jesudasen Appasamy. He did not, strictly speaking, aim to oppose the Hellenization of the dogma or to render it superfluous. Rather, his intent was to propose a modification. He suggested that the Son should be regarded as subordinate to the Father, with their relationship understood in moral rather than substantial terms.² The

² “This means that the relation between God and Jesus is a personal relation between Father and Son. Jesus also says: ‘The Father is greater than I,’ This

reasons for his proposal are well known, and are rooted more in Hindu categories than in Christian theology.³ Yet the effect of such a view is unavoidable: it reduces the Son to a creature and Christianity to a purely moral system stripped of salvific power. The second case is Pandipeddi Chenchiah, who seems to embody the hard form of critique. He believed that dogma unjustly and inappropriately constrained the free life of the Spirit. For Chenchiah, what truly mattered was the personal experience of Christ. As he wrote, “Church doctrine and dogma, whether from the West or from the past, whether from Apostles or from modern critics, are to be tested before they are accepted.”⁴ Like Appasamy, Chenchiah opposed the doctrine of the consubstantiality of the Son with the Father. He wrote, “Jesus as portrayed in the records is less than God ... We seek to keep both God and Jesus separate from each other and [hu]man from both.”⁵ Chenchiah understood Christ as “partaking [of] the immortal nature of God.”⁶ In essence, Christ is immortal, but He is not God.

These cases illustrate some of the main ramifications of the Indian theological critique of dogma. First, dogma is seen as constructed on Greek formulas that make little sense in the Indian context. Second, since these formulas are derived from Greek categories rather than biblical language, they are judged to lack authority. This was, for example, the position of Chenchiah. From this perspective arises the idea of developing a distinctive Indian dogmatic (or at least

shows that He regards Himself as wholly dependent upon the Father: He is not identical to the Father.” See: A.J. Appasamy, *The Gospel and India's Heritage* (London and Madras: SPCK, 1942), 36.

³ Robin Boyd, *An Introduction to Indian Christian Theology* (Delhi: ISPCK, 2009), 120.

⁴ Pandipeddi Chenchiah, “The Christian Message in a Non-Christian World,” in *Rethinking Christianity in India*, ed. A.N. Sudarisanam (Madras: Sudarisanam, 1939), 150.

⁵ Pandipeddi Chenchiah, “Jesus and Non-Christian Faith,” in *Rethinking Christianity in India*, 54.

⁶ Chenchiah, “The Christian Message in a Non-Christian World,” 166.

systematic) theology that draws on indigenous systems of thought. These positions seem to go more in the direction of the soft form of critique. Third, personal experience of encountering God is regarded as primary, taking precedence over metaphysical questions. Fourth, dogmas are unnecessary because they can never fully grasp the mystery of revelation. At best, they are only partially useful, since they provide approximate expressions of truth, but cannot be regarded as complete or definitive accounts of divine reality. These positions, instead, go in the direction of the hard form of criticism.

The issue of accepting dogma in general and that of accepting the Nicene dogma in particular, are two related but distinct problems. One may affirm dogma broadly while still struggling with Nicaea's specific articulation. In the cases of Appasamy and Chenchiah, however, uneasiness with dogma as such leads to a direct rejection of the Nicene teaching on the ontological union of the Son with the Father. The consequence, in both instances, is a Christology without salvific power. If the Son is not truly God, He cannot save. One may reasonably affirm that the central problem of Indian theology lies in the question of Christ's nature – true man and true God – which serves as a response to Hinduism's enduring dilemma of the dichotomy between God and the world.⁷ This concern explains the persistent theological return to the Council of Chalcedon. Yet the question of the Son's relationship to the Father is equally crucial, not only for establishing the Son's full divinity, but also for safeguarding His mediatory and salvific role.

These earlier criticisms have been retrieved and reformulated in more recent times. For example, Felix Wilfred framed the critique of dogma in Hindu terms. He observed, “The Divine mystery is not considered as an object since, as the Upanishads put it, the divine mystery

⁷ Robin Boyd, *India and the Latin Captivity of the Church* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1974), 89.

is that which ‘cannot be known by thought, and whereby, they say, thought itself is thought.’”⁸ This statement leaves both possibilities open: either that dogma represents only an approximation to truth, or that it is not an approximation at all. Sebastian Painadath, SJ, argued that God is not only beyond the dogmatic formulations of Christianity, but beyond all religions altogether. This implies the existence of a single divine reality that, in some manner, informs every religious tradition. As Painadath writes,

Deus semper maior; God is ever-beyond: God is beyond all religions. No particular religion can ever claim to have fully grasped the ineffable mystery of the Divine; no religious Scripture can be seen as the depository of the ‘fullness’ of God’s self-manifesting Word ... The finite cannot fully reveal the infinite.⁹

From this perspective, the dogmas of the Church must be understood as partial expressions of revelation, valuable but necessarily limited in their capacity to contain the fullness of divine mystery.

The issue at stake here is the relationship between revelation and language. No one claims that the criterion of truth lies in language itself; rather, it resides in revelation. Language – whether in the form of theological formulations or dogma – can serve as an approximation to truth. Painadath rightly observed that the finite cannot contain the infinite; yet, one could argue that the infinite can still disclose itself through the finite, including through language. In other words, the authority of revelation rests in revelation itself, but revelation can nevertheless be mediated through dogma, while at the same time remaining autonomous and inexhaustible.

More recently, Jacob Parappally has taken up two of the major critiques of dogma. On the one hand, he acknowledges

⁸ Felix Wilfred, *Beyond Settled Foundations: The Journey of Indian Theology* (Madras: University of Madras, 1993), 182.

⁹ Sebastian Painadath, SJ, “God is Beyond All Religions,” in *Pilgrims of Dialogue*, ed. A. Pushparajan (Munnar: Sangam Dialogue Centre, 1991), 219.

its limits, stating that “it must be admitted that no dogma, however constitutive it is for our Christian faith, can exhaust the mystery of Christ.”¹⁰ On the other hand, he emphasizes the primacy of experience, affirming that “in Asia broadly and India particularly, thousands of people experience Jesus Christ beyond the boundaries of the church and its dogmas.”¹¹ Thus, Parappally’s position straddles both the “soft” and the “hard” forms of criticism. On the one hand, he acknowledges the theological indispensability of Christ and the central role of faith, but emphasizes the limits of dogma—echoing the “soft” critique that views dogmatic formulations as partial approximations of the mystery. On the other hand, by affirming that thousands encounter Christ “beyond the boundaries of the church and its dogmas,” he effectively resonates with the “hard” critique, which questions the necessity and binding authority of dogmatic formulations themselves. His grand view is that, while it may continue to nurture the faith of those already within Christianity, the dogma’s rigid and unalterable structure reflects a vision of Christianity anchored in the past, thereby hindering the emergence of a renewed expression of the faith that can engage meaningfully with new contexts and audiences.

The issue at stake here is the relationship between revelation and experience. One can easily envision a form of Church composed of all those – Christians and non-Christians alike – who have experienced Christ directly. This would be a Church grounded not in the “sacred,” but in “holiness.” By holiness, we mean the immediate relationship between God and humanity, a direct encounter that does not depend on institutional or ritual mediation. By contrast, the sacred refers to structures of mediation – rituals, doctrines, and institutions – that serve as channels between the divine and human beings. In this vision, the Church would be defined

¹⁰ Jacob Parappally, *Christ Without Borders* (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis, 2024), x.

¹¹ Parappally, *Christ Without Borders*, ix.

not by sacred mediation, but by holiness as the unmediated experience of God's presence in Christ. The Church would be primarily mystical rather than institutional, grounded in holiness as the unmediated experience of Christ's presence. Its soteriological character would be not denied but relocated: salvation would be mediated not through sacred structures, but through the direct encounter with the divine. However, irrespective of whether salvation is conceived as proceeding directly from Christ or as mediated through the Church, the primacy of Christ's salvific mediation must first be secured. This is precisely what the dogma of consubstantiality establishes. Consequently, the dogma proves indispensable, whether one envisions the Church in mystical terms or within a soteriological framework.

2. NICAEA

It is well known that the central issue at stake in the Council of Nicaea was the divine nature of Christ and His relationship to the Father. There was no disagreement on the divine nature of Christ—that much was accepted. The real theological question was *how* He was divine: Was the Son fully and equally God, as the Father is? Or was He a lesser divine being, like the angels? In other words, was the Son truly God in the same sense as the Father, or was the Father alone the one true God? Unfortunately, no detailed record of the theological discussions held during the council has been preserved. What we do know is that the real challenge consisted in articulating this answer to these questions with precision. The challenge was how to formulate the answer in a way that faithfully preserved its meaning against misunderstanding or distortion. The answer was articulated through the use of the Greek term *homoousios*, meaning “of the same substance.” Today we use the word “consubstantial.” To better grasp the meaning of consubstantiality, it is helpful to consider what Eusebius of Caesarea, bishop in Palestine and one of the Council

Fathers, wrote in a letter to his congregation. Eusebius sought to clarify the term “of the same substance” so that no one would misinterpret. He wrote that the emperor himself explained that

the term [*“homoousios,”* “of the same substance”] does not describe a bodily state or physical properties, and so it is not saying that the Son comes from the Father as a division of his being or as a cutting off from it. God's nature, he said, is not a physical or bodily thing, and so cannot possibly be in a physical state. Therefore, we can only understand such things in divine and mysterious terms.¹²

Eusebius argued that the phrase “of the same substance” should not be understood in physical or material terms—as if the Son were a portion cut off or divided from the Father. In fact, God's nature is immaterial and beyond physical categories. Therefore, the Son's consubstantiality with the Father must be understood to mean that Christ is not a created divine being, like an angel, but truly shares in the same uncreated divine essence as the Father. Here is Eusebius again, “That the Son is of the same substance as the Father ... simply implies that the Son of God has no resemblance to created things, but is in every respect like nothing but the Father who begot him, and that he is of no other substance but the Father's.”¹³ The consubstantiality between the Son and the Father, Eusebius concluded, is a mystery. The dogma of the consubstantiality of the Son and the Father is the language through which the Church has historically expressed its reverence before the mystery of the relationship between the Father and the Son.

Although the concept of consubstantiality was articulated in Greek, the question it sought to address had earlier origins

¹² Eusebius of Caesarea, *Epistula ad Ecclesiam Caesariensis* (Letter to his Church after the Council of Nicaea), in *Patrologia Graeca* 21:783–790, ed. Jacques Paul Migne (Paris: Imprimerie Catholique, 1857–1866).

¹³ *Ibid.*

in the Hebrew tradition—and, further still, in Canaanite thought. Almost 40 years ago, rabbinical scholar Alan Segal produced what remains the landmark study on the notion of a “second power in heaven” within Jewish thought.¹⁴ He demonstrated that this concept was not regarded as heretical in Jewish theology until the second century CE. Tracing its development carefully, Segal located its origins in the Second Temple period (around 200 BCE), and showed that its antecedents were already present in the Hebrew Bible. Key scriptural passages such as Dan 7:9-14; Ex 23:20-23; and Ex 15:3 provided the textual foundation for the idea. This second power in heaven was not conceived as an adversary to the first, but as a complementary figure—one who operated in harmony with, and as an extension of, the supreme divine authority.¹⁵

Michael Heiser, the late Old Testament scholar, argued that the two powers concept in Israelite religion has its roots in Canaanite tradition. In Canaanite belief, the high god El reigned as sovereign, while Baal acted as his vice-regent, the visible and active agent of divine rule. Israel reshaped this paradigm, not adding a second distinct god, but rather a second power, and identifying Yahweh as both supreme ruler and active vice-regent, thus occupying both roles at the head of the divine council (Ps 82:1: “God has taken his place in the divine council”).¹⁶ This produced a binitarian pattern in the Hebrew Bible: Yahweh appears both as the invisible, transcendent Spirit and as a visible, often human-like figure. Sometimes the two are portrayed together or distinguished; at other times, they merge into a single divine identity.¹⁷ During

¹⁴ Alan F. Segal, *Two Powers in Heaven: Early Rabbinic Reports about Christianity and Gnosticism* (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1977).

¹⁵ Segal, *Two Powers in Heaven*, 7.

¹⁶ For the option of a second god, see: Margaret Barker, *The Great Angel: A Study of Israel's Second God* (Louisville, KY: Westminster / John Knox Publishers, 1992).

¹⁷ Michael Heiser, “The Divine Council in Late Canonical and Non-Canonical Second Temple Jewish Literature,” Doctoral dissertation, University of Wisconsin-Madison, Madison, WI; Department of Hebrew and Semitic Studies, 2004.

the Second Temple period, Jewish thinkers speculated on the identity of the “second Yahweh,” proposing figures that ranged from divinized biblical heroes to exalted angels. At that time, such speculations were not deemed unorthodox.

The situation changed, however, when some Jews – namely the earliest Christians – identified Jesus with this accepted Jewish concept. This association explains how they could worship both the God of Israel and Jesus without acknowledging any other deity: Jesus was understood as the incarnate second Yahweh.¹⁸ New Testament scholars have suggested, in fact, that Christianity adopted the pre-existing framework of the two powers to the relationship between the Father and the Son.¹⁹ As Alan Segal showed, it was in response to this development that Judaism eventually declared the two powers teaching heretical, sometime in the second century CE.²⁰

In sum, the notion of two powers in heaven originated in Canaanite religion and was adapted within Israelite

¹⁸ Daniel Boyarin, “The Gospel of the Memra: Jewish Binitarianism and the Prologue to John,” *Harvard Theological Review* 94/3 (2001): 243-284; Andrei Orlov, *The Glory of the Invisible God: Two Powers in Heaven Traditions and Early Christology (Jewish and Christian Texts)* (London: T&T Clark, 2019); David E. Willhite and Adam Winn, *Israel's Lord: YHWH as “Two Powers” in Second Temple Literature* (Minneapolis: Fortress, 2024).

¹⁹ Larry W. Hurtado, “Jesus’ Divine Sonship in Paul’s Epistle to the Romans,” in *Romans and the People of God*, eds. N. T. Wright and S. Soderlund (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1999), 217-233; Larry W. Hurtado, “The Binitarian Shape of Early Christian Worship” in *The Jewish Roots of Christological Monotheism, Papers from the St. Andrews Conference on the Historical Origins of the Worship of Jesus*, eds. Carey C. Newman, James R. Davila, Gladys S. Lewis, and John J. Collins (Supplements to the Journal for the Study of Judaism; Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1999), 187-213; Darrell D. Hannah, *Michael and Christ: Michael Traditions and Angel Christology in Early Christianity* (Wissenschaftliche Untersuchungen zum Neuen Testament 109; Tübingen: Mohr-Siebeck, 1999); Jarl E. Fossum, *The Image of the Invisible God: Essays on the Influence of Jewish Mysticism on Early Christology* (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck and Ruprecht, 1995).

²⁰ Daniel Boyarin, “Two Powers in Heaven; or, The Making of a Heresy,” in *The Idea of Biblical Interpretation: Essays in Honor of James L. Kugel*, eds. Hindy Najman and Judith H. Newman (Leiden: Brill, 2003), 331-370.

tradition, where Yahweh was understood as both sovereign ruler and active vice-regent. This produced a binitarian pattern in Israel's Scriptures, in which Yahweh could appear both as transcendent Spirit and visible, often human-like figure. During the Second Temple period, Jewish thinkers speculated on the identity of this second Yahweh without challenging orthodoxy. The decisive shift occurred when early Christians identified Jesus with this figure, enabling worship of both the God of Israel and Christ. In response, Judaism formally declared the teaching heretical in the second century CE. Segal is insistent that the divinity of Christ did not emerge primarily from biblical references to the Son of Man (Dan 7:13-14, but also 1 Enoch (chapters 37-71) and 4 Ezra (2 Esdras 13), written in the Second Temple period, where the Son of Man becomes a title for a messianic or heavenly figure), but rather through a particular interpretation of certain Old Testament passages concerning the second power.²¹ The decisive separation between the Jews and the Christians, therefore, was rooted in divergent readings of these texts.²²

Segal demonstrated that the phrase "two powers in heaven" was rabbinic terminology already in use before and during the rise of Christianity. In fact, both Jews and Christians followed the pattern to defend their respective positions through the same concept. The two powers themes can be found almost everywhere in the New Testament. In his Letter to the Philippians, Paul appears to deny Jesus' equality with the Father: "Christ Jesus, who, though he was in the form of God, did not count equality with God a thing to be grasped" (Phil 2:6). Yet in his Letter to the Galatians, Paul seems to imply the opposite: "Why then the law? It was added because of transgression, till the offspring

²¹ Segal, *Two Powers in Heaven*, 210.

²² For a different opinion, see: Aquila H.I. Lee, *From Messiah to Pre-existent Son* (Wissenschaftliche Untersuchungen zum Neuen Testament 192; Eugene: Wipf and Stock, 2009).

should come to whom the promise had been made; and it was ordained by angels through an intermediary. Now an intermediary implies more than one, but God is one" (Gal 3:19-20). Some of the early Church Fathers referred to the concept in their writings indirectly, without using the precise term. Among them, Segal listed Justine and Origen. With reference to Justin, Segal wrote,

While it is clear that Justine is using "two powers" traditions to discuss Jesus, the traditions could have hardly originated with the identification of Jesus as [the second power] ... Justin is taking over a previous exegetical, possibly mystical tradition, applying the name of his particular savior [i.e., Jesus], and defending his belief against the other candidates for the office.²³

Justin argued that Jesus is the one who fulfills the role of the second power, thus defending Christianity against alternative Jewish and gnostic interpretations that assigned the role to someone else. In his *Dialogue with Heraclides*, Origen explicitly stated that "in one sense we may speak of two Gods, yet in another sense of one God."²⁴ He thought, in fact, that the Son of God could be called a *deuteros theos* (a second god).

If one follows the line of thought advanced by Segal and subsequent scholars who developed his hypothesis, the theological dilemma faced by the Nicene Fathers comes into sharper focus. The dilemma hinged on the meaning of the expression "second Yahweh." If the incarnate Son is identified as the second Yahweh, does that mean He is to be understood as the distinct second power in heaven within the one God, or as a separate, second god? The central issue was not whether the Son was divine or subordinate to the Father, but rather whether the Son must be considered distinct or separated from the Father. At the time, diverse

²³ Segal, *Two Powers in Heaven*, 224.

²⁴ Origenes, *Dialogue of Origen with Heraclides in Alexandrian Christianity*, eds. J. Chadwick and J.L. Oulton (Philadelphia: The Westminster Press, 1954), 438, 1:124-125.

interpretations of the Son's relation to the Father circulated. Some claimed that the Son was identical with the Father, the very same essence without distinction.²⁵ At the other end of the spectrum, there were those who argued that Jesus was nothing more than a human being, who was deified after his resurrection.²⁶ By the second century, the controversy had crystallized into two possibilities: was the Son distinct from the Father and therefore of the same essence, or was He a second god—no longer merely distinct, but entirely separate? For the Nicenes, the answer was decisive: only one divine Being exists, and the Son must therefore be the second power of that one God—distinct but of the same essence. The Arians, however, maintained that the Son was a separate divine Being. The debate thus turned on ontology. If the Son is distinct but not separated from the Father, then He shares the same substance (*homoousios*) and, like the Father, is eternal, immortal, impassible, and immutable. But if the Son is a separate divine Being, as the Arians insisted, He must have been generated by the Father, since only one Being can exist without cause. In that case, the Son possesses a different substance: still divine, yet subordinate to the Father.

The solution proposed by Athanasius – the doctrine of *homoousios* – offered an answer to the theological dilemma by drawing on Aristotelian categories. Importantly, *ousia* (“substance”) was not a scriptural term, but a philosophical one. The term itself had already appeared in earlier writers such as Irenaeus and Origen, though never with the radical force it would acquire at Nicaea. In Aristotle, the phrase *kath' hauto* (“according to itself,” or “in itself”) is central to his definition of *ousia* (substance). In *Metaphysics* (esp. Book Zeta, 1028b–1032a), Aristotle explains that the primary sense

²⁵ I refer to Noetus of Smyrna, who is mentioned in Hippolytus, *Against the Heresy of Noetus*, Ref. 9.

²⁶ For example, Theodotus, who is mentioned in Hippolytus, *The Ante-Nicene Father: Translations of the Writings of the Fathers down to AD 325*, eds. A. Roberts and J. Donaldson (New York: Scribners, 1899), Ref. 7, 36.

of *ousia* is that which exists *kath' hauto*, independently, as a determinate being. Each *ousia* is uniquely itself and cannot be identical in essence with another, since identity of *ousia* would imply numerical identity of being. This is why, within Aristotle's categories, the idea that two beings share the same substance would appear contradictory: if they share the same *ousia*, they are not two beings but one. Thus, when the Nicene Fathers employed *homoousios* to describe the Son's relation to the Father, they deliberately chose the term *homoousios* to clarify that the Father and the Son are not two separate beings.

At the Council of Nicaea, Greek philosophy was placed at the service of resolving a theological problem of Semitic origin.²⁷ Yet it was also mobilized in response to an even greater challenge—one might say an existential question for Christianity itself. The Council of Nicaea represented an existential turning point for Christianity. The Council Fathers affirmed the salvific mediation of Christ. In doing so, they secured the very foundation of Christian faith: that salvation comes through Christ precisely because He is fully God, consubstantial with the Father. Looking back in retrospect, the Council was not just about settling a theological dispute, but about safeguarding the very possibility of Christianity. Had the proposal affirming the Son as a separated divinity been adopted, the Church would have effectively denied His full salvific capacity. Such a Son could not serve as the mediator of salvation in the fullest theological sense because He was not God, thereby undermining the very foundation upon which the Christian faith is constructed. In this sense, the Nicene affirmation of Christ's full divinity was not merely a doctrinal clarification but the preservation of the entire soteriological and theological architecture of Christianity.

²⁷ Giulio Maspero, “Nicaea: Hellenizing the Faith or Utilizing Philosophy?” *Communio: International Catholic Review* 51/4 (2024): 672-684.

Summarizing: Eusebius tells us that the Nicene dogma is not a formula in the strict sense, but rather a phrase that signals a mystery. It expresses a general interpretation of the Son's relation to the Father. The issue itself arose centuries earlier, when Judaism assimilated and reshaped a certain Canaanite conception of divinity. That conception became the model on which the earliest Christology of the nascent Church was built, and also the framework along which Judaism and Christianity eventually diverged. At Nicaea, the Fathers simply affirmed their conviction that the Son is distinct from the Father but not separate, and therefore shares His very nature. They did so by employing a Greek philosophical expression. Their decision, however, permanently established the truth that salvation comes through the mediation of the Son, precisely because the Son is God.

3. BACK TO INDIAN THEOLOGY AND DOGMA

As mentioned, the purpose of this article is not to provide a historical study of the Council of Nicaea as such, but to use it as a case study for engaging with the broader critique of Christian dogma in Indian theology – particularly in its soft and hard forms– and assessing whether, at least in this instance, the critique is valid. This article argues that, in the case of Nicaea, the “soft” form of the critique may hold merit, whereas the “hard” form does not. In fact, the issue of Hellenization remains a matter of discussion, though of only marginal significance; at the same time, the dogma itself is theologically indispensable.

This argument directly challenges the notion that the Hellenistic form of a dogma necessarily compromises its truth or renders it culturally parochial. In this case, the Hellenization of dogma is evident, but ultimately of secondary importance. The Nicene formula used Greek philosophical terms, but its real significance lay not in Greek thought itself, but in the theological conviction that the Son is truly God—distinct yet

not separate from the Father, and essential to salvation. The Greek categories made the doctrine's expression possible, but the decisive concern was theological and rooted in the Jewish tradition. Thus, Hellenization is evident but secondary to the deeper truth being affirmed. The Council Fathers deliberately retained this language as the most effective means, within their historical and linguistic context, to safeguard and express the salvific reality of Christ. The historical form of expression can be contingent while the theological content remains universal. If the critique holds that the dogma's Hellenization necessitates its reframing in non-Greek – specifically Indian – terms, but the Hellenization is, in fact, of only marginal significance, then the conclusion would be that a full-scale reframing is not the dogma's theological substance while expressing it in Indian conceptual and linguistic forms for the sake of clarity and accessibility, rather than because its original formulation is theologically flawed.

The truth of a dogma endures despite changes in language because its essence does not reside in linguistic formulation. To claim that the truth of dogma depends on the words used would imply that its content could be altered or manipulated. Yet what defines a dogma is precisely its resistance to such manipulation: its truth remains intact, transcending the particular terms chosen to express it. This means that dogma is not reducible to the words or philosophical categories (like Greek or Latin, or Indian) in which it has been historically expressed. Its center of gravity – the essential truth it affirms – transcends language. The wording may be imperfect, culture-bound, or even contested, but the theological content endures. Attempts to reformulate or reinterpret dogma may alter its expression but cannot change its essence. In fact, a dogma proves itself as dogma precisely by resisting reduction to linguistic manipulation: the truth it preserves remains stable even when the linguistic or cultural forms shift.

It also challenges the implication that such dogmas are dispensable or merely optional for contexts outside the West. The definition of the Son's consubstantiality with the Father did not emerge primarily from a speculative synthesis of the Gospel with Greek philosophy, but from the urgent need to preserve the integrity of the Christian faith itself. The dogma of the Son's consubstantiality is a doctrinal necessity for the coherence of the Christian faith. If the Son were not consubstantial with the Father, He could not be fully salvific; and without a fully salvific Christ, the entire theological structure of Christianity would collapse. Without that dogma, the very questions of how the Son relates to the Father and whether His role is truly salvific would remain unresolved, leaving the foundations of Christian faith uncertain and open to destabilizing interpretations. The Nicene affirmation of consubstantiality is not a relic of Greek thought but a doctrinal cornerstone without which the Christian faith would lose its very foundation. Therefore, the hard form – arguing that the dogma is dispensable – fails in this instance, since removing the dogma would collapse the faith's foundational claim about salvation itself.

CONCLUSION

This brief study on the Council of Nicaea and the dogma of consubstantiality aligns more closely with the position that advocates for the reinterpretation of dogmas in culturally specific terms, albeit with certain qualifications, rather than with the view that would dispense with the dogmas altogether. In fact, the “hard” form of the critique fails to recognize the non-negotiable place of the Nicene dogma within the architecture of Christian faith. The “soft” form, while legitimate in its aim of cultural translation, must acknowledge that what is to be reformulated is not a culturally bound opinion but a doctrinal cornerstone whose truth is universal. The real task, therefore, is not to reformulate the dogma, but to engage in a faithful inculturation that communicates its salvific truth within the conceptual and linguistic frameworks of the Indian context.